

Recommended citation: Morell, L., Cukierman, U., Vendrell-Vidal, E., Buxeda, R., Saliceti, L., Sjørnsen, H., Rivera-Gallego, W., Guzmán, M. F., Correa, L., & Palmieri, J. M. (2019). Was it worth it? Results of an engineering educator capacity building program. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1763-1772). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14657205.

Was It Worth It? Results of an Engineering Educator Capacity Building Program

L Morell

InnovaHiEd, Beihang University
Mayagüez, Puerto Rico

H Sjursen

New York University
New York, USA

U Cukierman

Universidad Tecnológica Nacional
Buenos Aires, Argentina

W Rivera

Universidad de Puerto Rico –
Mayagüez
Mayagüez, Puerto Rico

E Vendrell

Universitat Politècnica de València
València, España

MF Guzmán

Universidad Nacional de Tucumán
Tucumán, Argentina

R Buxeda

Universidad de Puerto Rico –
Mayagüez
Mayagüez, Puerto Rico

L Correa

Universidad Tecnológica Nacional
Buenos Aires, Argentina

L Saliceti

Universidad de Puerto Rico –
Mayagüez
Mayagüez, Puerto Rico

JM Palmieri

Universidad Tecnológica Nacional
Buenos Aires, Argentina

Conference Key Areas: Lifelong Learning, Talent Management

Keywords: STEM Educators, STEM Pedagogy, Faculty Capacity Building, Faculty Training

ABSTRACT

Many institutions and organizations provide engineering (and STEM¹) educators capacity building programs around the world. Some of these programs are short, other are longer, some are mostly theoretical, others include hands-on, practice-based activities. This paper presents the results of a newly developed capacity building program for STEM educators, the International Engineering Educator Certification Program (IEECP). After briefly describing the program content and teaching methods, the paper summarizes the hard outcomes as well as the results of a survey undertaken to understand the lessons learned by participants. The survey included data on participants' previous knowledge in pedagogy, their capacity building experiences, as well as an exploration of program learning outcomes and the deliverables required. Perceptions on the quality and usefulness of learnings and activities are also be discussed. Analysis of the survey results indicate the IEECP achieved its objectives, was well received by participants and had an impact on participants academic life.

¹ STEM stands for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The engineering educator capacity building program and motivation for the study

Developing capacity of STEM educators at all levels is one of the first priorities of many countries and regions worldwide to ensure economic and well-being of knowledge economies. In the USA for example, the White House's recent report on its STEM education outlines the vision and strategic planning to advance "the innovation capacity of the United States—and its prosperity and security — depends on an effective and inclusive STEM education ecosystem [1]. This report sets out a Federal strategy for the next five years based on a Vision for a future where all Americans will have lifelong access to high-quality STEM education and the United States will be the global leader in STEM literacy, innovation, and employment. It represents an urgent call to action for a nationwide collaboration with learners, families, educators, communities, and employers—a "North Star" for the STEM community as it collectively charts a course for the Nation's success.

In Europe, there are also different initiatives coordinated and supported by the European Commission (EC) on STEM main issues: the low attractiveness of these studies and the lack of professionals well prepared to cover labour-market needs. As an example, SCIENTIX [2] is a long-term project supported by the EC that promotes and supports a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM teachers, education researchers, policymakers and other education professionals. Recently, Scientix has issued some reports that summarize STEM education policies and practices in Europe.

Another interesting initiative is the STEM Alliance [3]. This is an initiative that brings together Industry, Ministries of Education and education stakeholders to promote STEM education and careers to young Europeans and address anticipated future skills gaps within the European Union.

Similarly, other nations like Singapore and India, are undertaking like-focused approaches to develop STEM human resources. Research shows that faculty development programs have been growing globally [4] and many institutions and organizations are providing engineering (and STEM) educators capacity building programs around the world as part of this transformation.

Building faculty capacity to address the higher education STEM challenges associated with these initiatives is of paramount experience. The United Nations Development Programme [5] defines capacity-building as: "the process through which individuals, organizations and societies obtain, strengthen and maintain the capabilities to set and achieve their own development objectives over time". Central to such capacity building is transformation, or the changing of mindsets. Changing mindsets takes buy in, ownership of process, knowledge and practice.

In 2016, **InnovaHiEd**, a consulting and capacity building group [6] developed the **International Engineering Educator Certification Program (IEECP)** [7] and was authorized by the International Society for Engineering Pedagogy (IGIP) [8] to establish an IGIP Center to provide training to STEM faculty to obtain IGIP's International Engineering Educator Certification. The hybrid, hands-on, practice-based

program and its components and unique requirements and implementation is described in a recent paper [9]. Teaching methods utilized in the IEECP include face to face lectures/workshops, flipped learning, teaching/learning with technology, reflection (developing a teaching portfolio), proposal writing, project implementation and peer-reviewed paper writing and submission. The IEECP has been offered twice to about 75 STEM deans and faculty members in the years 2017 and 2018. As part of the program's continuing quality improvement process, in addition to the cohort assessments carried as part of the delivery itself, program's leaders wanted to understand the hard outcomes and the lessons learned by participants. Therefore, in the Spring of 2019, a survey was distributed to all the program participants in the two cohorts mentioned above to collect data on their perceptions on the quality and usefulness of learnings and activities undertaken by the program in order to reflect and make decisions to improve future offerings. A total of forty five (45) survey replies – a sixty percent (60%) response - was received. This paper summarizes the analysis and conclusions of the survey results.

1.2 Objectives questionnaire

This study is a follow-up to participants of the International Engineering Educator Certification Program for the cohorts of 2017 and 2018. A survey was developed with the goal of understanding the impact of this faculty development program in providing a capacity building to the participants. *Fig. 1* provides the schematic representation of the survey sections. The questionnaire consisted of three parts: (1) understanding the profile of the participants prior to attending the program, (2) assessing the program effectiveness, and (3) determining faculty interest in continuing educational training development and institutional impact. In the first part of the survey, we wanted to assess our participant's level of exposure to pedagogical methodologies, their experiences in using them in their classrooms, and in publishing experience in pedagogy and innovative educational projects prior to the program. The second part of the survey focused on the program's deliverables. Participants were surveyed with regards to the program structure in areas such as organization, length, educational objectives, planning, added values of the program, and instructors' performance. Furthermore, participants provided their input with respect to program ability to improve their teaching and learning capabilities, classroom implementation experiences and the development of an innovation project that could result in a peer-reviewed publication. The third part of the survey was to inquire about the program effectiveness in provoking the participants the desire for continuous improvement in STEM pedagogical education. Among the areas to be surveyed were included those of trainings that participants would like to address and potential challenges in participation in educational trainings.

For the most part, participants in both cohorts were quite appreciative of the program and believe it will strengthen their teaching practice. Here is one testimonial: *"I wish to give thanks for all that I have learned. I have been able to implement some of the things I learned [in the program] and wanted to share the happiness we are witnessing daily with the outcomes. Change is really happening... and for me, one of those for which change is difficult, the fact that I am able to share with two colleagues has made your "teaching tips" easier to implement. Thanks for everything"*².

² Daniel Echaradía, UNS, Argentina, 2018 Cohort

Fig. 1. Schematic of the questionnaire’s sections.

2 PARTICIPANT’S PROFILE

2.1 Learning styles

As part of understanding our participants profile, a learning style inventory was performed. The Felder and Silverman learning styles test [10] was used to understand the preferred learning styles of the population. Fig. 2 shows a predominance of active, sensorial, visual, and global learners among thirty-eight (38) participants learning styles test results.

Figure 2 Preferred Learning Styles of Participants (n=38)

As can be seen in Figure 2, all learning styles were represented in the population. This important information was used to determine the program’s teaching strategies to be used to ensure that all the preferred learning styles benefited from the program’s teaching methodology. Course participants were made aware that both instructors and students learning styles preferences are to be considered when teaching methods are selected.

2.2 Teaching experiences prior to participating in the program

The participants represented an interdisciplinary population of STEM disciplines with 66.7% from engineering, of which 29% had less than ten years of teaching experience. Although 88.9% of the participants indicated having previous experiences using active learning and taking courses or training on pedagogy, about half (49%) had published peer-reviewed papers on STEM education. Furthermore, 53.3% had not published articles related to pedagogical innovation. *Table 1* shows the profile of the respondents.

Table 1. Participant’s profile prior to training.

Profile	Percent of respondents
Disciplines of participants	66.7% engineering
	6.7% sciences
	17.8% mathematics
	8.8% education
Years of teaching	60% over 15 years
	11.1% 11-15 years
	15.6% 6-10 years
	13.3% 0-5 years
Respondents with previous experiences with student-centered teaching	88.9%
Participants with available of pedagogical training centers at the participant’s institution	57.8%
Respondents that had published peer-reviewed papers in STEM education research articles in pedagogical innovation	46.7%
Faculty with previous courses or training in pedagogy	82.2%

2.3 Experiences during the program

The IEECP curriculum consists of twenty ECTS³ to be completed in a minimum of eight (8) months [6]. While the participants of the two cohorts being studied (2017 and 2018) took longer than eight months only seven percent (7%) of the participants considered that the program was too long. The program used a learning management system (LMS) to communicate with students and as the teaching/learning and assessment platform. All the program’s materials and resources were available to participants. Eighty four percent (84%) of the respondents rated as useful or very useful the use of the LMS.

Since the program is learned-centered and was developed on the philosophy of learning by doing, each module requires the participants to implement the learning

³ ECTS = European Credit Transfer System

experiences in their classrooms. Eighty-four percent (84%) of the participants considered that program requirements and workload to be appropriate in order to accomplish the program’s educational objectives and that all or most of the program instructors taught them what they preached.

Furthermore, eighty one percent (81%) of the respondents considered that the organization and planning of the learning experience were appropriate or very appropriate. The overall level of satisfaction of the participants of the program is reflected in two ways: ninety three percent (93%) would recommend the program to their peers, and, all respondents evaluated the IEECP as good or very good.

Concerning participants’ motivation during the program, ninety-eight percent (98%) of the respondents expressed that they felt very motivated or motivated, and, one-hundred percent (100%) felt that the program transformed their teaching-learning experiences at different levels. Ninety five percent (95%) of respondents experienced a high level of transformation due to the program and eighty eight percent (88%) considered that the pedagogical knowledge acquired as result of this training was good or very good.

Fig. 3 shows the respondents assessment of the most valuable experiences of the program. Over sixty percent (60%) considered that the planning and implementation of an innovation project and the development of an outcomes-based program/course were the two of the most valuable experiences. These were followed by learning about the innovation process, teaching/learning methodology and learning from colleagues/peers.

Fig. 3. Most valuable experiences of the program.

Since the program was structured in modules it was important to assess the perception of the participants to learning experiences in each module. *Fig. 4* indicates participant’s appreciation of the modules they enjoyed and learned the most. The modules of fundamentals of assessment, outcomes/competency-based curriculum, course management, and teamwork received over 50% acceptance.

Fig. 4. Program modules that participants considered as a high-level learning experience.

After completing the program, participants were assessed with regards to their use (or planned use) of teaching-learning methodologies. Fig. 5 indicates that the predominant teaching-learning methodologies participants were using include active learning, teamwork, and flipped learning.

Fig. 5. Teaching-learning methodologies which are being used or are being planned to be used by participants.

One objective of the program was to facilitate that all participants developed and implemented an educational innovation project. Except for three respondents (who are still working on their projects at the time of the writing of this paper), all participants developed and implemented an innovation project either in their classrooms, in a program or at the institutional level. Some of the innovations involved: student-centered mathematics teaching, collaborative design of rubrics between faculty and students, hybrid teaching in mathematical analysis, innovation in the learning outcomes, assessment of a mathematics course for engineering programs at three

Latin American universities, development of soft skills, and the use of LMS in the elaboration of practical projects in an introductory engineering course.

Another objective was that the innovation project was to be presented in a conference and/or a peer-review article to be submitted for publication. Thirty-three (33) of the forty-three (43) respondents have presented or submitted a paper to peer-reviewed journals about their innovation project. Overall, sixty one percent (61%) of the participants considered that they had satisfactorily achieved the majority of the program objectives, while thirty percent (30%) considered achieving all of the objectives, and nine percent (9%) considered having partially achieved the objectives (we assume these are the ones that are still working on some of the program's required tasks). Ninety one percent (91%) of the respondents have completed or are in the process of completing the Ing.Paed.IGIP certification.

More than fifty percent (50%) expressed that the program changed their attitude towards the social responsibility of engineers in such a way that the topic should be included as part of the engineering courses. In addition, eighty one percent (81%) considered that the program experiences allowed them to change their perception in that the engineering education should be linked to other disciplines in order to allow the development in students of political and social competencies, as well as soft skills. The respondents felt that engineers must increase their collaboration with IT and data management, digital art & design, life sciences, business and the social sciences (*Fig. 6*).

Fig. 6. Program participants perception of linking engineering to other disciplines.

2.4 Future plans

After completing the program, ninety three percent (93%) of respondents continue to practice innovations in their classrooms and/or working on an innovation paper. Eighty one percent (81%) plan to continue training in STEM education and pedagogy. Among the areas of education that participants would like to continue to learn are active learning and curriculum development based on outcomes, and, planning for accreditation. Some of the challenges that respondents believe they will be facing in

their continuous education include availability of time, economic resources and workload. Besides the topics covered in this Program, some other topics respondents would like more training include: industry-university collaborations, outcomes-based accreditation, integrating 4th industrial revolution, big data & artificial intelligence into the curriculum, best practices in faculty evaluations, project-based learning, Learning Factory, CDIO and EPiCS, the Global Challenges Scholars Program, STEM student retention, and, analytics in higher education.

Finally, eighty eight percent (88%) indicated that they are planning to continue participating in engineering education conferences and learning from colleagues.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The International Engineering Educator Certification Program (IEECP) offered by InnovaHiEd is an academic program that provides training to STEM faculty in order to obtain IGIP's International Engineering Educator Certification. It is a hybrid, hands-on, practice-based program that includes face to face lectures/workshops, the use of teaching/learning technology, the development of a teaching portfolio, a teaching innovation project proposal and a peer-reviewed paper writing and submission.

After completing two cohorts of the IEECP, some conclusions can be extracted according to a survey completed by a significant number of participants:

- The IEECP is well focused and organized, achieving its objectives and was accepted and appreciated by student participants.
- The planning and implementing of an innovation project as well as the development of an outcomes-based program/course were the two of the most valuable experiences.
- The IEECP transformed all the participants' teaching-learning experiences at different levels.
- Some of the IEECP's modules need to be further assessed in content and delivery.
- IEECP participants were very motivated during the learning experience, plan to continue to further their knowledge and education in pedagogy areas and are practicing what they learned in the program or are planning for the incorporation of learnings into their academic life.
- This research demonstrates that new effective teaching methods need to be used to ensure learning objectives. These must be based on ample research on learning effectiveness that emerges from learners' preferred learning styles. These include hands-on practiced based learning, reflection, community learning, using technology for communication between instructor-students and to enhance learning experiences and the awareness of the needs of industry and society to transform the engineering curricula and students' learning process.
- This study confirms what engineering education societies like the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE) [11], the European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) [12], Scientix [2] and the International Society for Engineering Pedagogy (IGIP) [8] promote among its members: the need of and facilitation of STEM educators capacity building.
- Finally, this study confirms that this program was worth it for student participants!

REFERENCES

- [1] Charting a course for success: America's strategy for STEM education, Report by the Committee on STEM education of the National Science and Technology Council, December 2018. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/STEM-Education-Strategic-Plan-2018.pdf>
- [2] SCIENTIX. The community for science education in Europe. <http://www.scientix.eu>
- [3] STEM Alliance – inGenious Education and industry. <http://www.stemalliance.eu/>
- [4] M. F. (. J. E. G.) Alenoush Saroyan (Editor), Building Teaching Capacities in Higher Education: A Comprehensive International Model, Stylus Publishing, 2010.
- [5] United Nations Development Programme. (2009). Capacity Development: A UNDP Primer. New York: Author. https://www.undp.org/content/dam/aplaws/publication/en/publications/capacity-development/capacity-development-a-undp-primer/CDG_PrimerReport_final_web.pdf
- [6] www.innovahied.com
- [7] www.igip.education
- [8] International Society for Engineering Pedagogy - IGIP," [Online]. Available: <http://igip.org>
- [9] Morell, Lueny, Uriel Cukierman, Eduardo Vendrell, Rosa Buxeda, Wilson Rivera and Harold Sjursen, A Developmental Framework for Teaching Expertise for Engineering and Related Disciplines, 2018 WEEF Conference Proceedings, Albuquerque, New Mexico, USA.
- [10] <https://www.webtools.ncsu.edu/learningstyles/>
- [11] American Society for Engineering Education - ASEE [Online]. Available: www.asee.org
- [12] European Society for Engineering education - SEFI [Online]. Available: www.sefi.be